

ADAPTATION TO EXPERIENCE LEVEL BASED ON USER'S SEARCH STRATEGY

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ABSTRACT

Decision making in large, information-intensive domains is discussed in terms of information gathering strategies employed by experienced, intermediate, and novice decision-makers. Differences by level of experience were predicted for seven strategies. These predictions were tested in a process tracing experiment employing a submarine search scenario. Differences were found among groups. These were 1) in the use of information gathering strategies, 2) in responses to written questions, and 3) in the content of recorded verbal protocols.

The experimental results were used to build an expert decision aid which adapts dynamically to the experience level of its user. This is done by tracking information gathering behavior and adapting the system response when the behavior was not expert-like. One unique aspect of this system was the use of the situational model to also model user behavior.

INTRODUCTION

Decision-making in large, information intensive domains can be partially characterized as an information assessment activity. When the information about a domain is complex, ambiguous, and changes dynamically, a good understanding of the situation can prune the possible response choices. Understanding the situation can be very difficult under such conditions. Decision making may therefore be best supported and aided by excellent information presentation incorporating what is known about appropriate search strategies and information structuring. To devise such a decision aid requires a knowledge of what are appropriate information search strategies.

To make the problem more difficult, decision makers differ in many ways and their search strategies also differ. Some of these differences may be critical to good decision making; others are irrelevant. Ideally, a decision aid should accommodate differences that are irrelevant and adapt in such a way that relevant differences are reduced.

Differences due to level or type of experience are especially interesting in this context because this variable so clearly impacts decision performance. Moreover, it is not uncommon for decision makers who differ in their past experience to be tasked with performing the same job. For example, submarine officers may differ in their training (college major, naval speciality, e.g., navigation or sonar),

kind of experience (ships, oceans, types of missions, time at sea), and/or length of service.

The project reported here used a process tracing [1] experiment to examine differences in information search strategies due to level of experience and applied the findings to the design of an adaptable decision aid for submarine officers. The submarine problem is representative of a class of decisions in which the situation information is ambiguous and changes dynamically. This ambiguity makes situation assessment, and specifically information gathering, critical to decision making.

Before discussing strategies, the experimental task will be described. Subjects were given a screen (see Figure 1) which allowed them to access information typically found in a command center. For ease, we shall define the following terms: *item* refers to any one item of information; *look* refers to a single instance of accessing (looking at) an item; *adjacent* (abbreviated adj) refers to any transition between adjacent items; *history* (abbreviated hist) refers to transition between two adjacent items when the item name is the same; item and look will be subscripted in matrix notation, thus look_{ij} will refer to a look at item_i at time_j. Items #1-4 were processed data, commonly referred to as system solutions; items #5-8 were raw data from sonar. The scenario used three segments, with the third segment being more difficult than the first two. Between segments subjects answered questionnaires designed to capture their recall of the given data, situation assessment, and next decisions.

	Time1	Time 2	Time 3	Time 4	Time 5	Time 6	Time 7
Item 1	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Item 2	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Item 3	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Item 4	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Item 5	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Item 6	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Item 7	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Item 8	■	■	■	■	■	■	■

Figure 1, Sample display screen. Subjects saw actual information rather than "Item #."

The experienced decision maker, like the expert problem solver [2] knows where to look for relevant information [3] and has expected patterns or schema which guide information search and assist recall of relevant data [4]. In contrast, the search patterns of the novice were

predicted to be less structured and identifiable. From past research [5,6] and our own observational studies and interviews, we were able to predict that subjects would differ in their use of several specific strategies. The results of the experiment, reported in full in [7], are summarized in Table 1. For the purposes of adaptation, the most important of these were the tendency of novices to depend on computer processed data versus the tendency of experts to make equal use of raw and processed data; the tendency of novices to use a greater quantity of data; and the tendency of experts to follow a structured search path.

Table 1
Search strategies and results

Strategy	Measure	Goal	Results*
Quantity	$Q = \sum(\text{look}_{ij})$	Look at as much as possible	N - high I - low E - lowest
Relook	$R = \sum(\text{look}_{[ij-1]})$	Re-examine items	Little difference
History	$H = \sum(\text{look}_{\text{hist}})$	Examine data history	E - high I - low N - lowest
Ease	$Ea = \sum(\text{look}_{\text{adj}})$ $E2 = Ea - H$	Move between items as quickly as possible	On Ea, no differences N - high, E - low on E2
Class	$C = \sum(p) \equiv \sum(r)$	Look at items of both raw & processed data	E - $p \equiv r$ I - $p > r$ N - $p > r$
Set	$S\{x, y\}$ such that transition time is short	Examine related data	E - many I - some N - few
Reliability	S such that $R\{p1, r1\}$	Check reliability of p1 using r1	E - yes I - some N - no

*N=Novice, I=Intermediates, E=Experts

These findings were used to develop methods for identifying users' search strategies and adaptively aiding users who differ in the efficiency of their information search behavior. Two additional results have implications for the development of adaptive decision aids. First, the appropriateness of the decisions made by experts did not differ from that of intermediates, unless the task was difficult. Second, there was greater within-group variation for the expert group than for the other two groups. These findings imply that appropriate, real-time adaptation must be more than tagging the user with an assessment of his or her "expertise." Consequently, the expert system developed [8] for this project recognizes variations in user information search strategies without assuming the user's experience level. It individually tailors responses to alleviate difficulties found with non-expert-like strategies. A primary goal of the expert system was to provide a co-operative decision making environment which allowed the user more input into the decision process. As a bonus, we

believe that such a system can reduce the user acceptance problems commonly found with expert systems. The system, called Ranger, addresses the submarine target ranging domain.

The knowledge base, consisting of the decision making environment, was modelled as a network with three levels of objects storing information in increasing states of processing (Figure 2). Each object can contain any number of related pieces of information and the objects are connected with a message passing system. Data from the lower objects serve as input to higher objects. Higher objects require sets of data from lower objects to produce processed information. As data become available, intermediate results are generated and conclusions are reached. All data, intermediate results and conclusions are stored within the network and the same network serves as a model of the current situation in the domain.

Figure 2: Representation of the decision making environment knowledge base

The task facing the decision maker is to efficiently access the necessary information, without examining extraneous items. To accomplish this, the user is able to access information at any stage of processing, that is, from anywhere in the network. Ranger monitors the user's information search pattern by maintaining several measures of user-computer interaction. These measures include 1) what information has been queried, 2) repeated or redundant queries, 3) amount of information queried, 4) type of information (raw vs. processed) requested, 5) sequences of information queried, 6) completeness of sets of information requested, 7) time between queries, 8) consideration of historical changes in data values, 9) reliability checks of computer generated results, and 10) use of computer-generated explanations. These measures were derived from the process tracing experiment and provide a means for recognizing differences in users' information search strategies. Each network object stores user monitoring measures for its own information items.

Thus, the same network (see figure 3) also serves as a model of the user based on the user's pattern of information queries. This model is the key to Ranger recognizing the need for adaptive responses. By comparing the system's reasoning model with the user's reasoning model, Ranger can recognize inconsistencies and recommend corrective actions to the user. Figure 4 depicts the process Ranger follows for such comparisons. Ranger records where the user is in his/her decision making, how he/she arrived at

that point, and, by projecting forward in the network, can predict where he/she is going. When the user is querying in a non-expert-like manner, Ranger suggests a more expert-like approach and continues to monitor the user to determine whether or not such suggestions were employed. Table 2 summarizes user actions, implications, and types of user adaptation.

Figure 3: Reasoning models

Figure 4: Comparison Process for Adaptation

Table 2
Adaptation Examples

User Actions	Implications	Ranger's Responses
User querying is unstructured	User does not have structured search strategy.	Alert user to valid search paths
User fails to query critical information	User does not know what information is important	Alert user to key data
User persists on unsupported path; has seen contrary evidence	User does not understand data - conclusion relationships	Review prohibitive data and data-conclusion relationships
User persists on an invalid path; has seen supporting evidence	User is being misled along path that unseen data prohibits	Alert user to invalidity of the path, provide an explanation
User does not persist on good path; has seen supporting evidence	User does not understand data-conclusion relationships	Review supportive data-conclusion relationships
User queries conclusions without seeing inputs	User may not fully understand conclusion	Provide the conclusion, explain derivation
User is following a valid, structured path of queries	User is correcting assessing the situation	Provide answers, only

The aim of Ranger was to allow users to interact with the computer flexibly, employing their own individual problem solving strategy. Users are not forced to conform their strategy to that of the expert system and are allowed to follow the development of the problem's solution. Ranger monitors the user and adaptively responds when the user's pattern of queries is inconsistent with the system's expectations. The result is a co-operative decision making environment in which the user has an active role in the solution's development and the system facilitates efficient information search while allowing flexibility.

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